

The Influence of Human Resource Management Practices on the Performance of Academic Staff in Morocco Higher Education Sector

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Abstract: Tertiary Institutions, such as universities, aid in developing highly skilled technological capabilities and future leaders who have the knowledge and abilities necessary to promote economic growth the growth of a country. By executing the curriculum created for this goal, universities, as educational institutions, are tasked with preparing young people to contribute to national growth in the future. The main aim of the study is to determine the impact of HRM practices on employee performance of academic staff in Moroccan universities. Three elements; compensation, work environment, and training and development were found to be the best predictors of academic staff performance in a particular Moroccan institution in Marrakesh, Morocco. Three public universities (Univer1, Univer2, and Univer3) were chosen. Out of the 400 questionnaires that were issued, 250 were declared legitimate for the final analysis, and 300 were returned. The application of multiple regressions analysis showed that training and development has positive and statistically significant effect on of the academic staff in Moroccan university. Also, work environment has positive and statistically significant effect on of the academic staff in Moroccan university. Compensations was also statistically significant.

Keywords: Training and Development, Compensation, Work Environments, Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The major goal of founding a university is to promote learning and the dissemination of knowledge that will benefit humanity (Hashim, 2019). Universities are also expected to be creators of manpower and custodians of literature for the expansion and advancement of nations. They must also attract, create, encourage, and sustain a motivated workforce to aid in the achievement of their goals and objectives (Hashim, 2019). It is anticipated that human resources management (HRM) will significantly improve the effectiveness of a company (Olatoye et al, 2020). Tertiary Institutions, such as universities, aid in developing highly skilled technological capabilities and future leaders who have the knowledge and abilities necessary to promote economic growth the growth of a country.

By executing the curriculum created for this goal, universities, as educational institutions, are tasked with preparing young people to contribute to national growth in the future (Olaosebikan, 2020). The significance of universities as a subset of institutions offering tertiary education in a developing nation like Morocco cannot be highlighted enough (Olaosebikan, 2020). Tertiary Institutions, such as universities, aid in developing highly skilled technological capabilities and future leaders who have the knowledge and abilities necessary to promote economic growth the growth of a country (Olatoye et al, 2020, p.218).

In order to fulfil organizational goals and objectives and ensure employee job satisfaction, human resources management (HRM) is concerned with how well employees perform on the job. Employees must act in a certain way to achieve pre-established objective work behaviour, which must be addressed and continually monitored to prevent it from degenerating into pitfalls in company goals and targets (Olufadi et al, 2022). Employees are directly impacted by human resources management, which influences things like the type of employment, compensation, and career opportunities. Without the requisite combination of material, financial, and human resources, universities cannot function efficiently. Because they organize all other resources toward the achievement of the institution's goals, human resources are among these three that are most valuable to every organization (Olatoye et al, 2020, p.219).

Employees, both academic and non-academic staff included, are regarded as one of the most valuable resources in any university (Olatoye et al, 2020, p.219). Therefore, if these academic and non-academic personnel are taken care of through the implementation of globally recognized management techniques that will pay attention to and engage in workplace skill development, they could function as a tool for the competitive advantage of the institution over others (Olufadi et al, 2022). While non-academic employees play a vital and major role in administering and managing the university, academic staff (line structure) is what propels the institution's overall success in terms of research, teaching, community growth, and reputation. Understanding how HRM techniques might be applied to raise academic staff productivity in Moroccan universities is crucial.

1.1 Problem Statement

In addition to managing corporate leadership and culture and assuring compliance with employment and labour regulations, human resource management (HRM) practices are in charge of recruiting, selecting, training, evaluating, and rewarding personnel (Olufadi, et al, 2022, p.295). A number of reactions have been made in response to the mounting challenges brought on by the quick changes in the education sector (Kolawole, 2020, p.142). Globalization of education, the pace of technological advancement, and rising demand for high-quality education, among other things, have all enhanced the dynamism of the competitive environment to which the education sector must adapt (Kolawole, 2020, p.143). Existing data points to the potential of this field of study. Previous research was largely conducted in western and Asian Pacific with different institutional framework compared to Morocco. This study will help to close this knowledge gap and lay the groundwork for understanding key aspects of HRM practices that affect the performance of academic staff in the Moroccan university system.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The main aim of the study is to determine the impact of HRM practices on employee performance of academic staff in Moroccan universities. In order to achieve the overall aim, the following independent objectives would be examined.

RO: To determine the influence of training and development on the performance of academic staff in Moroccan universities.

RO: To determine the influence of work environment on the performance of academic staff in Moroccan universities.

RO: To determine the influence of employee compensation on the performance of academic staff in Moroccan universities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Academic Staff Performance

Employee Performance is a measure of how well an employee performs their duties and complies with any rules, standards, or obligations placed on them by their employer. Performance is the result of an employee's actions and abilities in a given setting (Nwamadi & Ogbonna, 2021, p.243). It is an act and demonstration of worker skill. A person's performance as an employee is the outcome of the work he or she does in relation to his or her role in the organization. Employee performance is a joint outcome of effort, aptitude, and task perception (Nwamadi, 2021, p.243). A variety of factors, including managerial standards, knowledge, talent, and commitment to a certain work, affect employee performance. In the context of university academic staff, performance may be measured in terms of teaching, research and community development, which ultimately affect the reputation of the university. The capacity or skill of the

individual to perform the job and the motivation to employ this talent or skill in the actual performance of the job can both be considered to be functions of the person's performance on the job (Nwamadi & Ogbonna, 2021, p.243).

Performance is the result of information that has been accessible and used on the job to its fullest potential which bring improved organizational outcomes in terms quality, efficiency and effectiveness of services or products offered (Ekundayo & Ajayi, 2009). This particular dimension is critical in the university settings where different components of the university interact to deliver value to the people. However, effective adoption of relevant HRM practices is important to achieve desired employee performance in the university.

2.2 Training and Development and Employee Performance

In order to increase employees' performance both now and in the future, it is essential to use training and development to provide them with the knowledge, skills, and abilities they need as well as to change their attitudes and behaviours (Okechukwu, 2017). It helps to increase employee productivity both personally and organizationally (Okechukwu, 2017). It is essential for any business since it requires not only altering employees' knowledge, values, and behaviours but also getting them to adopt new technology, boosting both personal and business productivity (Khan & Tang, 2016). Studies have shown that training and development are positively connected with employee work performance (Singh et al., 2020). Although, substantial evidences suggest that training and development is positively related with range of organisational outcomes such as: commitment, retention and positive work attitude, majority of the previous were done in Western and Asian Pacific region; hence this study will bring additional insights and perspectives from Morocco.

H1: Training and development has positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.

2.3 Work Environment and Employee Performance

The office environment has a significant impact on how each person behaves. As a result, the effectiveness of the workplace has an impact on employees' drive to work hard, efficiency, and performance. Workplace environment characteristics have an impact on employees' willingness to remain motivated, innovative, involved with coworkers, and devoted to their jobs. The workplace environment has a significant impact on an employee's success or failure (Zhenjing et al., 2022, p.2).

It is simple to realize that a company's workplace culture influences employees' performance, but it is far more difficult to comprehend how this affects productivity and employee satisfaction. The workplace has a growing amount of significance in the modern society. Because of all the distractions at work, it might be difficult for us to concentrate on what we are doing. Companies must create a positive work atmosphere for their employees if they want to guarantee that they have a productive day at the office (Zhenjing et al., 2022, p.2). Work environment includes both the physical features and structure communication and relationships which influence work employee work behaviours in the university. Improvising the work environment in the university would have positive and significant effect on academic staff performance.

H2: Work environment has positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.

2.4 Compensation and Employee Performance

The foundation of a successful workforce is frequently compensation, which is the incentive provided to employees in exchange for their efforts. Your company's personnel pool's performance and quality are typically strongly correlated to how successfully you implement your pay planning tactics (Rana & Malik, 2017). A compensation package need not always be accompanied by financial rewards. It also covers medical coverage, work-life balance, flexible benefits, and employee incentives (Khan et al, 2019). Employees of today prioritize other facets of remuneration just as much as they do financial compensation (Olufadi et al., 2022, p.298). According to Rana and Malik. (2017), organizations compensate their employees for demonstrating a willingness to perform various jobs and services for them. Khan et al. (2019) noted that compensation may consist of both monetary and non-monetary benefits; monetary benefits include pay and bonuses, while non-monetary benefits consist of additional vacation time and other leisure activities. Providing workers with alluring financial incentives is essential for achieving high job performance at work (Rana & Malik, 2017)

H3: Compensation has positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.

Figure 1: Research farmwork

3. METHODOLOGY

After the literature study, three elements; compensation, work environment, and training and development were found to be the best predictors of academic staff performance in a particular Moroccan institution in Lagos State. Three public universities (Univer1, Univer2, and Univer3) were chosen. Out of the 400 questionnaires that were issued, 250 were declared legitimate for the final analysis, and 300 were returned. Last but not least, pilot research was conducted on a sample of 60 workers (20 responders from each university). With input from three university professors, the pilot study served as the foundation for rephrasing several of the phrases that the respondents found unclear. The experts' insights helped to shape the final research questions.

3.1 Measurement

The items used in evaluating the variables were chosen from previously validated measures tested on a five-point Likert scale of increasing-increasing order (1=strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree). This is consistent with the quantitative deductive stance of the study. According to numerous social scientific and educational studies, reliability measures that are greater than 0.6 are often favoured (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). Five questions from Opadeyi and Akpa (2021), which were modified, were used to measure training and development and work environment respectively. Five items, modified from Nzewi et al. (2015), were used to test compensation and performance.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Reliability analysis

Statistical Analysis

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Variables	No of items	Cronbach alpha (N=250)
Training and development	5	0.8102
Work environment	5	0.8561
Compensation	5	0.9073
Academic staff performance	5	0.8463

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According to the reliability data in Table 1, all four constructs were determined to be reliable because each one has a reliable value of at least 0.7, which is the cutoff mark in many social sciences and education-based studies (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). The highest value, 0.9073, belongs to employee compensation, which is followed by the work environment (0.8561), academic staff performance (0.846), and training and development (0.8102).

Table 2: Regression Model (Model Summary)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error
0.712	0.507	0.501	0.33507

According to the data in Table 2, the "R" value of 0.712 denotes a sound regression model, and the R square represents the variance explained by the three independent variables. This means that the three independent variables training and development, and compensation explained 71% of the variation in employee performance.

Table 3: ANOVA (Multiple Regression)

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	28.435	3	9.475	84.395	0.000
Residual	27.619	246	0.112		
Total	56.044	249			

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), training and development, Compensation, Work environment).

Table 5 shows that three independent variables, which means that (Training and development, compensation and Work environment) significantly predicted employee Performance because the test statistic is significant at a 0.05 level of significance ([F (3, 249) = 72.006, p= 0.000].

Table 4: Multiple Regression coefficients

	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient		
	B	St. Error	B	t	sig
(Constant)	1.422	0.202		7.030	0.000
Training and development	0.209	0.039	0.279	5.382	0.000
Compensation	0.011	0.040	0.013	0.265	0.003
Work Environment	0.493	0.044	0.552	11.240	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE

Multiple regression analysis on Table 4 shows that, training development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance ($\beta=0.279$, $p<0.005$). Compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance ($\beta=0.013$, $p<0.005$). Finally, Work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance ($\beta=0.552$, $p<0.005$).

Table 5: Hypotheses decision

No	Hypotheses	Decision
H1	Training and development have positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.	Accepted
H2	Work environment has positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.	Accepted
H3	Compensation has positive and significant impact on the performance of the academic staff in Moroccan universities.	Accepted

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the findings on Table 5, it was found that training and development has positive and statistically significant effect on of the academic staff in Moroccan university. Also, work environment has positive and statistically significant effect on of the academic staff in Moroccan university. Compensations was also statistically significant. The above results suggest the followings: First, the positive and statistically significant effect of training and development on the performance of academic staff is indicative that, training and development is critical to devalue new knowledge, skills and abilities which will enable the lecturers to deliver improved research and teaching in the universities. The finding of this aligns with the results from Opadeyi and Akpan (2021), Obaze and Samikon (2022), that training and development are essential in building competitive human resource that will achieve strong organisational outcomes in terms of performance and productivity.

Secondly, the positive and statistically significant effect of work environment on academic staff performance is suggestive that an engaging work environment is vital to achieving desired performance outcomes from the academic staff. This finding is consistent with the results from Adom (2018), Chiekezie et al (2017). Another human resource strategy that has demonstrated a favourable correlation with performance is compensation. Through a variety of organizational behaviours, such as dedication and strong organizational citizenship, people respond to relevant organizational interventions in terms of monetary rewards in an appropriate manner (Park & Shaw, 2013; Park, et al., 2018). This result is in line with the social exchange theory's postulate, which holds that if a worker feels that his or her compensation structure is fair and equal, that individual will be more inclined to accept relevant organizational tasks and duties.

6. CONCLUSION

The primary goal of the study is to look into how career advancement, pay, and engagement affect academic staff performance in Moroccan universities. The study's conclusions demonstrate that career advancement, pay, and the workplace environment have favourable and significant influence on academic staff performance in Moroccan universities. In order to attract and keep top performers in their organizations, managers and executives should make sure that strategic career development, a competitive compensation structure, and quality engagement are all included in the new and evolving human resource policy.

Although career advancement and pay are important for employee performance, the level of engagement that employees have with their work determines how much individual innovation they are prepared and willing to contribute to the firm. Employee engagement at its highest-level results in the achievement and perhaps even maintenance of desired organizational outcomes. According to the study's findings, the employee work environment has the highest correlation value and the highest individual effect on the multiple regression, which suggests that if managed and carried out effectively, Moroccan universities will achieve high academic staff performance levels.

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